

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

DATAMITE Meet Up event

On 6 February, the DATAMITE project hosted the **DATAMITE Meet Up event** at the [OTE](#) headquarters in Athens, Greece, under the theme 'Bridging Research and Industry in EU-funded Innovation'.

Bringing together Europe's leading innovators, researchers, policy makers and industry leaders to foster collaboration, accelerate data-driven progress and create a unified strategy for Europe's digital future, the event was a **unique networking opportunity** bringing together researchers and industry professionals involved in EU-funded projects. **The event was livestreamed.** If you missed it, you can watch it on [our YouTube channel](#).

[Read the full article](#)

DATAMITE at the Data Spaces Symposium

The [Data Spaces Symposium](#) took place on 11-12 March in Warsaw, Poland. Hosted by the [Data Spaces Support Centre](#) and the [Data Spaces Business Alliance](#), it is the premier global event dedicated to the future of data spaces, bringing together the brightest minds, **leading innovators and pioneering organisations** to shape a connected, data-driven world.

As in previous editions, **DATAMITE did not want to miss out on this important event** in the world of the European data economy and the development of [European data spaces](#), two of the fundamental pillars of the project. This year **DATAMITE participated in the Data Spaces Symposium with various sessions and a booth**, through several of its consortium members.

[Discover more](#)

PROJECT CONTRIBUTIONS

DATAMITE Demos

As DATAMITE is in its final year, our modular, open source, multi-domain framework for improving monetisation, interoperability, trading and data exchange has moved from theory to practice. In order to show all aspects of the framework and the different functionalities it offers, the **technical partners** responsible for its development **will record several demos**. A [playlist](#) has been set up on the DATAMITE YouTube channel, where the demos will be added as they are completed. For now, **these are the ones you can already watch**, all made by the Centre for Research and Technology HELLAS (CERTH):

DEMO: Data Product Composition tool - Building a DATAMITE product.

DEMO: Anonymisation tool - Anonymise a DATAMITE data product.

DEMO: Data Product Composition tool - Data products derived from heterogeneous data sources.

Deliverable 4.1 Strategies for Improving Data Monetization

In the second half of December 2024, the **DATAMITE consortium** released a **new deliverable**: D4.1 Strategies for Improving Data Monetization.

This document outlines strategies for improving data monetisation, building on a comprehensive literature review and analysis of existing industry practices. It presents a framework that identifies and categorises various monetisation strategies based on a structured questionnaire, providing tools to enhance accessibility to the strategy topic for the users of the platform. Among these tools are a 4x4 Pathway Matrix and a questionnaire designed to guide organisations in selecting appropriate monetisation approaches. These tools facilitate effective data utilisation, ultimately driving value creation and fostering a sustainable data economy. The framework serves as a practical guide for

organisations seeking to optimise their data monetisation efforts in a rapidly evolving market.

[Read the deliverable](#)

Deliverable 5.1 - Report on Framework Integration and Demonstrator Status (M26)

At the end of February, the **DATAMITE consortium** released a new **deliverable**: D5.1 Report on Framework Integration and Demonstrator Status (M26).

This document is a report on the status of the work package 5 activities regarding the set-up and maintenance of the continuous integration tools and processes that support and guide the integration and release of the DATAMITE framework. Furthermore, it covers the activities related to the six project use case demonstrators' developments, integration and testing as well as training material development.

[Read the deliverable](#)

Deliverable 5.3 - Pilot Demonstrators (M26)

At the end of February, the **DATAMITE** consortium released a new **deliverable**: D5.3 Pilot Demonstrators (M26).

The purpose of this document is to present the progress in integrating the key components of the DATAMITE framework and to verify the system's functionality within pilot deployments. The document aims to demonstrate how the DATAMITE solution performs in various operational environments, showcasing both the flexibility of its configuration and its ability to adapt to specific requirements – from deployments on cloud platforms to in-house solutions used for security and integration purposes.

[Read the deliverable](#)

SYNERGIES

The EUDATA+ Cluster

The EUDATA+ cluster brings together six data monetisation and data sharing projects driven by the European Commission to foster collaboration in programmes such as Horizon Europe. The cluster, consisting of **enRichMyData**, **UPCAST**, **PISTIS**, **Graph-Massivizer**, **FAME** and **DATAMITE**, drives common goals and knowledge transfer to maximise impact and foster the development of data-sharing technologies.

After participating in major events and conferences such as [EBDVF](#) or [Data Week](#), the cluster is taking a further step towards professionalisation and defining itself as an entity beyond the umbrella under which each project operates by creating its **own website and LinkedIn page**. Visit and follow them!

[Visit the EUDATA+ website](#)

[Visit the EUDATA+ LinkedIn](#)

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